

Experimental material for the paper

“Studying the Influence of Empathy Maps on Brainstorming for Requirements Elicitation: A Controlled Experiment”

This document presents the experimental material with which the subjects were provided. First, the global description of the exercise is presented, after which the problem statement (an information system for an Animal Adoption Centre - MODEPRAN) is introduced. Two examples are subsequently shown, one of an Empathy Map and another of the Personas obtained after the execution of the experiment. Finally, an excerpt of the list of ideas of requirements obtained by one working group in the brainstorming session is shown.

Note that the participants received examples of Empathy Maps, Personas and ideas of requirements from a domain other than that of the Animal Adoption Centre. However, in this document, in order to show part of the results of the experiment, we show an actual Empathy Map, Personas, and ideas of requirements (excerpt) produced by one of the working groups in the experiment.

1. Exercise description

Objective: the purpose of this exercise is to apply the Brainstorming technique in order to define the goals **and requirements of an information system**. This must be done by identifying **proposed ideas of requirements to** be taken into account for the information system to be developed.

Exercise context: the exercise will be carried out in a classroom session of the Requirements Engineering course by forming working groups of 5 or 6 people.

Material and resources to use: the slides of Topic 3 (Elicitation of Requirements) will be used, which include a description and examples of the techniques used (Empathy Maps, Personas and Brainstorming). There will also be an introductory video to the Brainstorming technique, which is available in the “resources section” of this course. Several *post-it* pads will be provided at the start of the session to facilitate the discussion of collaborative ideas and organise them. Finally, a laptop may also be used to document the outcome of the session and carry out consultations with external sources (such as websites similar to the exercise domain).

Expected Result: as a result of the Brainstorming session, the students must prepare and deliver an Initial Ideas of ***Requirements Document*** with the following structure:

1. Cover // *Including the names of the members of the group*
2. Purpose of the document
3. Description of the context of the system
4. System goals
5. Context diagram
6. Description of the PERSONAS identified
7. *Description of the Empathy Map (in the case of Group A)*
8. *Ideas of requirements (functional), including their description and priority*
9. *Ideas of requirements (non-functional or restrictions), including their description and priority*

Guide to defining the scope of the software system: the result of the Brainstorming session will be the *Initial Ideas of Requirements Document*. This document will include those ideas of requirements that the working group considers "achievable" with the resources available for the realization of the project (time, money, personnel, experience, ...).

Prioritize and filter the ideas of requirements in order to incorporate them into the Initial Ideas of Requirements Document. This activity is part of the Consolidation phase of the Brainstorming technique and the working group must work to "choose" those ideas of requirements considered most valid.

2. Problem statement. Animal Adoption Centre (MODEPRAN)

MODEPRAN (<http://www.protectoramodepran.com/>) is a Valencian non-governmental organisation dedicated to helping stray animals. This centre requires an information system with which to manage their daily activities more efficiently. Its main function is that of a refuge for animals rescued from the street and to enable their adoptions.

The application **must have a private** section in order to be able to keep track of rescued animals, veterinary care and regular vaccines and adoption processes (application, approval, delivery, monitoring). The centre also wishes to keep track of medicines and food that are purchased or received as donations. In addition to the MODEPRAN employees, the new application should also keep track of the volunteers, who must be registered to work regularly and have access to the facilities.

Finally, the application should also have a **public** section that will allow the animals that are available for adoption to be advertised and to raise funds through partners (with different modalities), sponsors (for specific animals) and specific donations, using different means (bank account, PayPal, credit card, etc.). Partners and sponsors must be able to register with the system.

Specific requirements are not previously defined, and MODEPRAN expects a proposal with ideas of requirements to help them gain greater visibility, carry out *fundraising and adoption campaigns*, and be able to automate most of their activities, taking into account a *minimal* investment owing to their limited resources.

3. Example of an Empathy Map

The Empathy Map shown in the following picture was developed by one of the working groups participating in the experiment. It shows an example of an Empathy Map of a stakeholder for whom the following was analysed: what they might do, say, think and feel with regard to the system described in the problem statement. It is in Spanish, in order to show an actual result of the experiment performed.

4. Example of Personas

The Personas shown in the following picture were developed by one of the working groups

participating in the experiment. It shows personal information, technology, and knowledge, motivations, and goals that are representative of a potential veterinary stakeholder. It is in Spanish in order to show an actual result of the experiment performed.

<p>Christopher se ha incorporado recientemente al mundo de la Medicina Veterinaria, apenas llega al año de experiencia. Actualmente tiene dos empleos simultáneos con el fin de obtener una mayor fuente de ingresos, por lo que apenas tiene tiempo libre.</p>		
	<p>Tecnología y conocimientos:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smartphone • Portátil Thinkpad • Competencias en Inglés e Italiano 	<p>Objetivos:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realizar consultas dinámicas y rápidas a todo tipo de animales domésticos. • Ser un buen profesional. • Enriquecer su conocimiento y experiencia a lo largo de los años.
<p>Christopher Moltisanti Profesional veterinario Edad: 31 años Ingresos: media</p> <p>Personal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Con pareja estable, sin hijos • Detallista y comprometido • Versátil 	<p>Motivaciones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Por un mundo sin animales enfermos. • Aspirar a tener un mejor puesto. 	

5. Excerpt of ideas of requirements

The following table shows an excerpt of the ideas of requirements obtained by a working group in the Brainstorming session. The ideas of requirements are categorised into the following categories: (a) People-centred; (b) Business-orientated; (c) Technology-orientated; and (d) Others.

#	Ideas of requirements	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
1	Emergency call: notifications by social networks and e-mail of the urgent need for help in the case of unexpected catastrophes (flood, fire,...).		x		
2	Sharing on social networks: to allow users to share information about Modepran (animals, events) on the most popular social networks.	x	x		
3	Stock management: inventory of feed, blankets and veterinary material		x		
4	Monthly planner: to allow users, volunteers / collaborators and employees to confirm their intention to attend an event or the shelter (to help out with cleaning or walks).		x		
5	Pet-care guide: tips on how to raise, care for and educate your canine / feline companion (FAQ)				x
6	Dashboard: collect and show information graphically about the stock, adoptions, economic situation, volunteers / partners ...		x		
7	Chat with the administration: to provide the option of starting a conversation with the people in charge of the shelter.		x		
8	List of other animal care centres: provide information about other centres in other cities or municipalities in order to raise the community's awareness.		x		
9	Web application and also available for smartphones (Android and iOS) to carry out all the management of adoptions, donations, etc.			x	
10	Modepran events can be created / modified / deleted only by users internal to the centre, but it will be visible to all types of users.		x		
11	The user will have real-time control (instant updates) over the status of an animal.	x	x		